

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

Emotional self-control and job performance in emotionally toxic organizational environments

Autocontrol emocional y desempeño laboral frente a entornos organizacionales emocionalmente tóxicos

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Abstract This research aims to analyze the influence of emotional self-control on job performance in organizational environments characterized by emotionally adverse dynamics, from a human talent management perspective. The study was conducted through a qualitative and exploratory literature review, based on the systematic analysis of scientific literature published between 2018 and 2024 in high-impact, indexed academic databases. The methodology allowed for the identification of theoretical and empirical trends related to emotional regulation, psychological well-being, and work behavior in complex organizational contexts. The results show that emotional self-control acts as a key psychological resource that modulates the relationship between adverse working conditions and performance, contributing to the reduction of stress, emotional exhaustion, and counterproductive behaviors. It is found that strengthening emotional competencies promotes stable performance and the psychological well-being of the worker, even in unfavorable organizational contexts. It is concluded that emotional self-control is a strategic component for the sustainability of job performance and should be integrated into human talent management and psychosocial risk prevention policies.

Keywords emotional labor, workplace well-being, psychosocial risks, organizational behavior, talent management.

Resumen La presente investigación tiene como objetivo analizar la influencia del autocontrol emocional en el desempeño laboral frente a entornos organizacionales caracterizados por dinámicas emocionalmente adversas, desde la perspectiva de la gestión del talento humano. El estudio se desarrolló mediante una revisión documental de enfoque cualitativo y carácter exploratorio, basada en el análisis sistemático de literatura científica publicada entre los años 2018 y 2024 en bases de datos académicas indexadas de alto impacto. La metodología permitió identificar tendencias teóricas y empíricas relacionadas con la regulación emocional, el bienestar psicológico y el comportamiento laboral en contextos organizacionales complejos. Los resultados evidencian que el autocontrol emocional actúa como un recurso psicológico clave que modula la relación entre las condiciones laborales adversas y el desempeño, contribuyendo a la reducción del estrés, el agotamiento emocional y las conductas contraproducentes. Se identifica que el fortalecimiento de las competencias emocionales favorece la estabilidad del desempeño y el bienestar psicológico del trabajador, incluso en contextos organizacionales desfavorables. Se concluye que el autocontrol emocional constituye un componente estratégico para la sostenibilidad del desempeño laboral y debe ser integrado en las políticas de gestión del talento humano y prevención de riesgos psicosociales.

Palabras clave trabajo emocional, bienestar laboral, riesgos psicosociales, conducta organizacional, gestión del talento.

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Introduction

Human talent management represents a strategic pillar for efficient organizational functioning, directly influencing job performance, productivity, and the overall quality of work environments. Within organizational landscapes characterized by high demands, constant pressure, and complex interpersonal dynamics, employee behavior cannot be explained solely by technical skills or specialized knowledge. Instead, it must be analyzed considering the diverse emotional processes that influence decision-making, interpersonal communication, and how employees cope with work demands. All these conditions justify the growing academic interest in emotional self-control as a key factor in human talent management, especially in the face of various emotionally toxic organizational environments.

Emotional intelligence is conceptualized as Sáenz-Cavia & Delfino (2025) the ability to receive, understand, regulate, and utilize one's own and others' emotions adaptively, guiding thought and behavior toward functional goals. Within this framework, emotional self-control becomes a central component of emotional intelligence, enabling individuals to appropriately manage their emotional reactions to situations of conflict, pressure, or negative feedback. Thus, emotions are not merely an obstacle to job performance; rather, they are a resource that, when consciously and correctly regulated, fosters mature, prudent professional behaviors geared toward achieving organizational results.

Numerous studies have demonstrated that emotional self-control is positively related to job performance and key variables in human talent management. These studies Miao et al. (2021) indicate that within organizational settings, employees with higher levels of emotional regulation exhibit better skills in conflict resolution, accepting feedback without personal interpretation, and maintaining functional working relationships, resulting in increased individual and collective performance.

On the other hand, Ramadhona et al. (2022) it states that the ability to manage emotions contributes positively to strengthening organizational commitment and reducing counterproductive behaviors associated with stress and job dissatisfaction. In other words, when emotions dominate an individual and there is no adequate emotional self-control, the likelihood of defensive reactions, interpersonal conflicts, and a deteriorating organizational climate increases, creating emotionally toxic environments.

Leal (2022) highlights that insufficient emotional regulation in the workplace negatively affects the quality of professional relationships, reduces openness to feedback, and impairs rational decision-making, thereby fostering confrontation, demotivation, and emotional distancing among organizational members.

From this perspective, within human talent management,

emotional self-control is associated not only with job performance but also with psychological well-being and organizational sustainability. Recent research shows that developing emotional competencies reduces emotional exhaustion and promotes job satisfaction, contributing to the creation of healthy and productive work environments De la Cruz (2019). Along these same lines, Persich et al. (2021) it is argued that skills such as emotional self-regulation, assertive communication, and the ability to avoid taking work situations personally constitute practical manifestations of emotional self-control in complex organizational contexts.

Some of these principles find conceptual correspondence with widely disseminated personal development approaches, such as those presented in *The Four Agreements* Ruiz (2023), particularly those related to emotional responsibility and the conscious interpretation of interpersonal messages. While this work does not belong to the scientific field, its postulates align with current theoretical foundations on emotional regulation and organizational behavior, reinforcing the idea that emotional mastery fosters more balanced and functional professional behaviors.

Despite the growing body of scientific literature on emotional intelligence and self-control, gaps remain in the theoretical integration of these constructs as explanatory factors for job performance in emotionally toxic organizational environments, especially in Latin American contexts. Consequently, it is necessary to delve deeper into the analysis of emotional self-control as a strategic element within human talent management, aimed at improving performance, strengthening the organizational climate, and promoting mature and responsible work behaviors.

According to the above, the present study aims to analyze the influence of emotional self-control on job performance in emotionally toxic organizational environments, based on a review of recent scientific literature, in order to provide theoretical foundations that support its incorporation into human talent management practices.

Methodology

This research was developed through an exploratory literature review, guided by a qualitative approach, focused on analyzing emotional self-control as an influential factor in job performance within emotionally toxic organizational environments, from a human talent management perspective. The collection and analysis of information combined theoretical and analytical methods, allowing for the examination, integration, and systematization of conceptual and empirical contributions from the specialized scientific literature.

The literature search was conducted in high-impact, indexed academic databases, including Scopus, Web of Scien-

ce, SciELO, Dialnet, and Redalyc, considering publications from 2018 to 2024 to ensure the currency, relevance, and scientific rigor of the selected sources. Additionally, widely recognized fundamental theoretical works on emotional intelligence and regulation were included to provide a conceptual framework for analyzing emotional self-control in the organizational context.

The methodological process was developed sequentially and systematically. First, the conceptual delimitation of the categories of analysis was carried out. These included: emotional self-control, job performance, emotionally toxic organizational environments, and human talent management, based on theoretical models and approaches recognized in the international scientific literature. Second, inclusion and exclusion criteria were established for the selection of documents, considering only scientific articles, empirical studies, and theoretical reviews published in peer-reviewed journals, and excluding non-academic literature or literature without verifiable methodological support. Third, the selected studies were subjected to an analytical, critical, and comparative reading, identifying conceptual approaches, methodological designs, and main findings related to the object of study.

Documentary analysis was used to analyze the information, allowing for the thematic organization of the content and the establishment of relationships between the analyzed categories. This procedure facilitated the identification of research trends, theoretical convergences, and knowledge gaps regarding the role of emotional self-control in preventing dysfunctional work environments and its influence on job performance. Furthermore, the analysis made it possible to compare the contributions of various authors regarding how emotional regulation helps mitigate the negative effects of emotionally toxic organizational environments on employee behavior and performance.

The research methodology was based on the methodological approaches of Grant & Booth (2009), who emphasize that analytical document reviews allow for a comprehensive understanding of the state of knowledge in a specific field, as well as on the proposals of Hernández-Sampieri et al. (2021) regarding the qualitative approach and the non-experimental, documentary-type design. This methodology ensured coherence between the stated objective and the procedure followed, allowing the study to be replicable and its results to serve as a basis for future empirical research on emotional self-control, job performance, and human talent management in complex organizational contexts.

Results and discussion

Analysis of the scientific literature revealed that emotional self-control has become a key determinant of job performance, particularly in contexts characterized by emotionally toxic organizational environments. The reviewed studies

consistently demonstrated that workers with higher levels of emotional self-control showed a greater capacity to regulate their responses to situations of pressure, interpersonal conflict, dysfunctional leadership, and negative work climates, which positively influenced their performance, emotional stability, and professional relationships.

Furthermore, the results indicated that a lack of emotional self-control was associated with increased impulsive reactions, recurring conflicts, emotional exhaustion, and decreased job performance, especially in organizations where toxic practices such as aggressive communication, excessive workload, and a lack of institutional support prevail. These conditions negatively impacted both individual performance and the collective functioning of the organizations (Kim, 2024).

The results showed a consistent, strong, and recurring relationship between emotional self-control and job performance, particularly in adverse organizational settings. The reviewed literature demonstrated that workers with greater emotional regulation skills were able to maintain adequate levels of productivity, commitment, and professionalism, even when exposed to emotionally toxic work environments. These findings concurred in indicating that emotional self-control acted as a protective psychological resource, allowing workers to cope with job demands with balance, responsibility, and emotional maturity, as presented in Table 1.

First, the studies analyzed showed a positive and significant relationship between emotional self-control and job performance, indicating that workers with a greater capacity to regulate their emotions tended to perform their duties with greater effectiveness, behavioral stability and results orientation, even in adverse organizational conditions (Li et al., 2018).

Furthermore, the findings related to managing work-related stress demonstrated that emotional self-control reduced the negative impact of pressure, overload, and interpersonal conflicts, fostering more rational and less reactive professional responses (O'Connor et al., 2019). This result showed that emotional regulation functioned as a coping mechanism in the face of dysfunctional work environments.

Regarding organizational commitment, the evidence indicated that workers with high levels of emotional self-control maintained a greater sense of responsibility and permanence in the organization, despite being exposed to toxic climates, reducing counterproductive behaviors such as absenteeism, demotivation, and direct confrontation (Zhu et al., 2022).

Furthermore, studies that addressed organizational climate indicated that emotional self-control helped mitigate the negative effects of emotionally toxic environments, promoting more respectful and functional work interactions, even when structural conditions were not favorable (Kim, 2024).

Table 1. Relationship between emotional self-control and job performance variables in emotionally toxic organizational environments

Variables analyzed	Main findings	Reference
Job performance	Significant positive relationship with emotional self-control	Li et al. (2018)
Managing work-related stress	Reduction of the negative impact of stress and organizational pressure	O'Connor et al. (2019)
Organizational commitment	Greater commitment and less emotional strain	Zhu et al. (2022)
Organizational climate	Mitigating the effects of emotionally toxic environments	Kim (2024)
Job satisfaction	Positive association with psychological well-being	Extremera et al. (2018a)

The results related to job satisfaction showed a positive association between emotional self-control and the psychological well-being of workers, which was reflected in higher levels of emotional balance, frustration tolerance, and satisfaction with the role performed (Extremera et al., 2018a).

Taken together, these findings confirmed that emotional self-control is a key factor in sustaining job performance and protecting the well-being of the worker in the face of emotionally toxic organizational environments, positioning itself as a strategic competency within human talent management.

The review results consistently showed that emotional self-control acts as a key protective factor against the harmful effects of emotionally toxic organizational environments. Several studies agreed that workers with higher levels of emotional self-regulation were able to maintain their job performance, even when exposed to dynamics characterized by authoritarian leadership, persistent conflict, psychological harassment, and hostile communication (Salanova et al., 2016; Alsomaidae et al., 2023).

Empirical evidence showed that emotional self-control allowed workers to dissociate negative emotions from their task performance, preventing emotional distress from leading to dysfunctional behaviors or work errors. In this sense, Bru-Luna et al. (2021) they maintain that the ability to regulate intense emotions acts as a psychological buffer that

reduces the likelihood of impulsive responses to adverse organizational stimuli.

The reviewed studies indicated that emotional self-control favored cognitive reappraisal processes, through which workers reinterpreted toxic situations in a less threatening way, reducing the impact of chronic stress and emotional fatigue (Sistiaga et al., 2025; Mazzetti et al., 2023). This mechanism explained why some employees managed to maintain acceptable levels of performance even in deteriorating organizational contexts; the main findings are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2 shows that emotional self-control plays a cross-cutting role as a protective factor against various manifestations of organizational toxicity. The reviewed studies agree that emotional regulation significantly reduces impulsive responses to workplace conflicts, thus contributing to more functional professional interactions (Sistiaga et al., 2025).

Coping based on self-control helps mitigate the effects of workplace harassment and toxic leadership, reducing emotional strain and the likelihood of counterproductive behaviors (Alsomaidae et al., 2023; Salanova et al., 2016). Taken together, the findings presented in the table show that emotional self-control not only protects the worker’s psychological health but also strengthens their resilience and adaptability in adverse organizational contexts (Mazzetti et al., 2023).

Table 2. Emotional self-control as a protective factor against toxic organizational environments

Variable analyzed	Main findings	Reference
Emotional regulation	It reduces impulsive reactions to workplace conflicts.	Sistiaga et al. (2025)
Psychological coping	It mitigates the effects of bullying and toxic leadership	Alsomaidae et al. (2023)
Emotional exhaustion	Reduces exhaustion and emotional fatigue	Salanova et al. (2016)
Counterproductive behaviors	Lower incidence of aggressive responses	Mazzetti et al. (2023)
Workplace resilience	Increases adaptability	Bru-Luna et al. (2021)

The results also identified that emotionally toxic organizational environments had a direct and negative impact on job performance when adequate emotional self-control resources were lacking. The reviewed literature described these environments as spaces characterized by dysfunctional leadership practices, lack of recognition, violent communication, favoritism, and excessive pressure for (Anjum et al., 2018; Rasool et al., 2021).

Several international studies have shown that prolonged exposure to these environments significantly increased levels of stress, work-related anxiety, and burnout, affecting concentration, decision-making, and the quality of work performed (Kaluza et al., 2020; Segura et al., 2025). In the absence of emotional self-control, these conditions led to a progressive decline in individual and collective performance.

In the Latin American context, research conducted in Ecuador, Colombia, and Mexico showed that organizational toxicity was associated with high rates of turnover, absenteeism, and interpersonal conflict, especially in organizations with limited emotional well-being policies (Márquez, 2020; Chumpén, 2024). However, these same studies highlighted that workers with greater emotional intelligence were able to partially mitigate these effects.

Table 3 clearly summarizes the main characteristics of emotionally toxic organizational environments and their direct effects on workers. It shows that practices such as authoritarian leadership, aggressive communication, and excessive workload generate significant psychological and behavioral consequences, including chronic stress, emotional exhaustion, and decreased job performance.

Lack of institutional support and a negative work environment are associated with demotivation, turnover, and reduced organizational commitment. These findings demonstrate that organizational toxicity not only affects individual well-being but also compromises the overall functioning of the organization, especially when effective emotional self-control mechanisms are lacking to mitigate these effects.

Another relevant finding was the direct relationship be-

tween emotional self-control and the worker's psychological well-being, understood as an essential component for the sustainability of job performance over time. The reviewed studies agreed that emotional self-control promoted a balance between job demands and personal resources, reducing the likelihood of burnout and work-related emotional (Bakker & de Vries, 2021; Chumpén, 2024).

Recent literature has highlighted that psychological well-being not only influences an employee's mental health but also their ability to maintain stable, creative, and collaborative performance, even in adverse organizational environments (Coronado-Maldonado & Benítez-Márquez, 2023). This aspect proved especially relevant in contexts where organizational toxicity could not be modified in the short term.

Similarly, the results showed that organizations that promoted emotional development programs indirectly strengthened job performance by providing workers with tools to manage negative emotions, conflicts, and work (Extremera et al., 2018b; Özer & Escartín, 2023).

Table 4 shows the close relationship between emotional self-control, psychological well-being, and the sustainability of job performance in adverse organizational contexts. The results reflect that the development of emotional self-control contributes significantly to reducing burnout, anxiety, and work-related depression, promoting a more balanced state of emotional health.

Furthermore, it is evident that psychological well-being translates into greater productivity stability, improved interpersonal relationships, and a positive impact on organizational results. Taken together, these findings confirm that emotional self-control not only acts as an individual protective resource but also as a strategic factor for promoting sustainable job performance, even in environments characterized by high levels of pressure and emotional toxicity.

The evidence analyzed confirms that emotional self-control is a central psychological mechanism for sustaining job performance in emotionally toxic organizational environments, acting as a mediator between adverse work condi-

Table 3. Characteristics of emotionally toxic organizational environments and their effects

Environmental characteristics	Effects on the worker	Reference
Authoritarian leadership	Stress and decreased performance	Anjum et al. (2018)
Aggressive communication	Interpersonal conflicts	Rasool et al. (2021)
Work overload	Emotional exhaustion	Kaluza et al. (2020)
Lack of institutional support	Demotivation and turnover	Segura Lozano et al. (2025)
Negative work environment	Reduction of commitment	Márquez Ortega (2020)

Table 4. Relationship between emotional self-control, psychological well-being, and sustainable performance

Dimension	Observed results	References
Psychological well-being	Reduction of burnout	Bakker & de Vries (2021)
Emotional health	Reduced anxiety and work-related depression	Chumpén Elera (2024)
Sustainable performance	Stability in productivity	Coronado-Maldonado & Benítez-Márquez (2023)
Emotional climate	Improvement of labor relations	Extremera et al. (2018b)
Organizational management	Positive impact on results	Özer & Escartín (2023)

tions and workers’ behavioral responses. This finding aligns with the postulates of emotion regulation theory, which maintains that the ability to modulate negative emotions allows for goal-oriented behavior even under pressure (Gross, 2024; Mazzetti et al., 2023)

However, this study offers a relevant nuance by demonstrating that self-control not only protects individual performance but also mitigates the systemic effects of organizational toxicity on the work environment and collective commitment. In contrast to research that primarily emphasizes the direct negative impact of toxic environments on performance (Anjum et al., 2018, Rasool et al., 2021) the results discussed broaden this perspective by showing that the presence of personal emotional resources introduces a differentiating effect on the work experience.

While previous studies describe a nearly linear relationship between organizational toxicity and performance decline, the present analysis suggests that this relationship is conditional and modulated by the worker’s level of emotional self-control. This interpretation partially coincides with the approaches of Bakker & de Vries (2021), but advances by explicitly integrating the component of performance sustainability in prolonged contexts of emotional adversity.

Furthermore, psychological well-being should not be understood solely as a consequence of the work environment, but as an active factor influencing the stability and continuity of performance. In this sense, the results align with the findings of Coronado-Maldonado & Benítez-Márquez (2023), who maintain that emotional well-being fosters adaptive work behaviors; however, the present study emphasizes that such well-being is largely sustained by internal processes of emotional self-control, even when organizational conditions are neither optimal nor modifiable in the short term.

From a critical perspective, the results also challenge organizational approaches focused exclusively on the structural transformation of the work environment, showing that, while such transformations are necessary, they are insufficient if they are not accompanied by the strengthening of individual emotional skills.

This position coincides with Extremera et al. (2018a) and Özer & Escartín (2023), but the differential contribution of the present work lies in emphasizing that emotional self-control should not be conceived as a passive adaptation strategy or as a normalization of toxicity, but as a transitory resource of protection while promoting deeper organizational changes.

In relation to the stated objectives, the results discussed allow us to affirm that the purpose of analyzing the relationship between emotional self-control, job performance, and emotionally toxic organizational environments has been met, demonstrating that this relationship is complex, dynamic, and mediated by psychological well-being. Furthermore, evidence is provided that reinforces the need to incorporate emotional self-control as a strategic competency within human talent management and the prevention of psychosocial risks, especially in Latin American contexts where dysfunctional organizational practices (Márquez, 2020; Chumpén, 2024).

However, it is necessary to acknowledge certain limitations of the study. First, as it is a literature review, the findings depend on the methodological quality and contexts of the studies analyzed, which may limit the generalizability of the results. Second, the heterogeneity of the instruments used to measure emotional self-control and organizational toxicity makes direct comparison between studies difficult. Finally, most of the reviewed studies have cross-sectional designs, which restricts the understanding of the long-term effects of emotional self-control on job performance.

Despite these limitations, the discussion allows us to conclude that emotional self-control emerges as a key element in understanding why some workers manage to maintain functional performance and relative psychological well-being in emotionally toxic organizational environments, while others experience significant deterioration.

This is relevant both theoretically, by integrating approaches to emotional regulation and organizational psychology, and practically, by guiding the design of organizational interventions that simultaneously consider the emotional de-

velopment of the individual and the transformation of the work context.

Conclusions

The study concludes that emotional self-control is a critical psychological resource for sustaining job performance in emotionally toxic organizational environments. The findings show that the ability to regulate emotions significantly shapes how workers cope with pressure, interpersonal conflict, and dysfunctional practices, confirming that job performance is influenced not only by technical or structural factors but also by internal emotional competencies. Emotional self-control contributes both to effective task execution and to the preservation of psychological well-being, reducing prolonged stress and the risk of burnout while fostering adaptive responses to adverse situations. Moreover, the results indicate that the impact of toxic organizational contexts on performance is conditioned by individual emotional resources, with emotional self-control acting as a moderating factor that mitigates harmful effects without legitimizing negative practices. Consequently, the study underscores the importance of strengthening emotional self-control as a strategic component of human talent management and psychosocial risk prevention to promote resilient, healthy, and sustainable work performance.

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Conflicts of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

Author contributions

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Data availability statement

The datasets used and/or analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

Statement on the use of AI

The authors acknowledge the use of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies to improve the readability and clarity of the article.

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